

FORM OF ACTIVITY IN SPORTS TOURISM

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Annotation: This article examines the forms of activity of sports tourism as a sport for people in various life conditions - from active recreation to the professional sphere of personal activity.

Key words: tourism as a sport, sports tourism, types of tourism, routes, refereeing.

Introduction. Sports tourism was previously considered as a fashionable hobby for young people, then sports tourism was positioned in the market of health services as an area of active recreation for the population [5, 6]. Recently, sports tourism has become increasingly important in the professional sphere.

The problem with all this is the lack of sufficient information and promotion of this sport. There is a need among young people to engage in this sport [1, 3]. A program with a clear mechanism for implementing this sport is needed. The participation of beginners and professionals are completely different things. Those who want to engage in this type of tourism do not know where to start, and do not have a sufficient level of physical fitness, which is necessary specifically for this sport [2, 4, 5].

Moreover, for a certain part of the population this sport should be positioned as a form of professional and active recreation activity.

Sports tourism is a sport based on competitions on routes that include overcoming obstacles in the natural environment categorized by difficulty (roads and trails with various surfaces and off-road terrain, crossings, passes, peaks, rapids,

canyons, caves) [7, 8, 10], at distances laid in the natural environment and on artificial terrain. A route is specified, a route to follow, with certain places.

This is the preparation and conduct of sports trips with the aim of overcoming an extended expanse of wild nature using rafting means (water tourism) or on foot in the mountains (mountain tourism).

There are two types of sports tourism: active and passive [9, 11, 12]. With an active type of tourism, the basis is the need to engage in some kind of sport. When passive, it is interest in the sport, observation. Sports tourism is a traditional form of activity. New forms of sports tourism have significantly revived it recently [10, 13, 14].

This is a sport whose main purpose is to cover a certain distance in a certain time with a certain set of obstacles in natural conditions with a high degree of autonomy. Sports tourism includes the following types of tourism: hiking, mountain tourism, cycling tourism, water tourism, horseback riding, auto tourism, caving tourism [15, 16].

Sports hikes are divided into categories of difficulty: from 1st - the easiest (you need to cover 100 km in at least 6 days in hiking) to 6th category - the most difficult. If the 1st and 2nd categories of difficulty are suitable for people in normal physical shape, then for the 3rd and above you must already be in excellent sports shape, have good endurance, knowledge and high moral qualities. Not everyone can withstand daily hard physical labor at the limit of their capabilities in a close team and when every drop of comfort is obtained through labor, while maintaining a positive attitude and first of all thinking about each other.

In sports tourism there are specialized professional titles associated with the right to carry out professional or teaching activities in the field of sports tourism: guide, instructor (senior instructor, international class instructor) of sports tourism. As in other official sports, in sports tourism there is organized and professional refereeing, the activities of which are regulated by relevant regulatory documents. By gaining experience in refereeing and undergoing the necessary professional training

(schools, seminars), judges acquire the corresponding judicial titles up to an international category judge. At the same time, a certain feature of refereeing in sports tourism is that the remuneration of sports judges is small or refereeing is carried out on a voluntary basis. Many of the judges are tourists themselves - athletes with extensive experience and significant sporting achievements. Sports judges in sports tourism, without exaggeration, are respected, honorable representatives of the sports community.

It should be noted that many tourists also engage in related sports: orienteering and multisport, rock climbing, mountaineering, rafting, mountain biking, alpine skiing, yachting and other types of active recreation and sports. Tourists are a reserve for training rescuers in the natural environment. Sports tourism - primarily sports hiking - is a team sport in which the traditions of mutual assistance and mutual assistance, sports discipline, self-improvement and mutual transfer of knowledge and experience are strong. The passion for sports tourism allows you to get acquainted with the culture and way of life of different countries and peoples, with wonderful and often even unique corners of nature, interesting sights, enjoy communication, and acquire reliable comrades.

Participation in sports hikes of initial categories of complexity and in competitions over distances, as a rule, does not require significant financial expenses, at the same time it allows you to gain the necessary basic skills and enjoyment of participating in hikes and competitions. Engaging in sports tourism as a complex sport carried out in a complex natural and social environment, of course, carries certain risks and requires the athlete to have versatile knowledge, skills, experience and good physical, technical and psychological preparation.

In large cities there are many physical education organizations of sports tourism and amateur tourist clubs, which, among other things, conduct schools for training tourism personnel. Studying in such schools is desirable, although not mandatory for tourism. That is why sports tourism is divided into different types: cycling, mountain, water, walking and others.

Combinations of these types are possible. But in any form, the main thing is the competitive component. There are more and more people wanting to engage in sports tourism. Moreover, this desire does not depend on social status, age and occupation. Sports tourism is the most democratic sport, balancing physical needs with material capabilities.

Many people who want to join this sport do not know where to start so as not to cause harm to their health. We recommend starting to engage in tourism with the most accessible type - hiking sports tourism. It is healthy, low-cost and does not require special training, as in other types of tourism.

Conclusion. It should be noted that some types of sports tourism are not only traumatic, but also dangerous to human life as a whole. Therefore, these types of tourism should be carried out with specialists and in special equipment. Moreover, certain areas can be pursued by professionals to perform vital tasks and improve professional skills.

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